

EXPLORING THE LINKS BETWEEN AI USE, METACOGNITIVE STRATEGIES, AND COGNITIVE ENGAGEMENT IN STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION

Nigyn J. Epino and Judith C. Chavez

Lourdes College Incorporated, General Capistrano Street, Cagayan De Oro City, Philippines, 9000

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ABSTRACT

Reading comprehension in the age of artificial intelligence (AI) requires both cognitive engagement and the use of metacognitive strategies that promote active monitoring and evaluation of learning. With AI tools increasingly integrated into academic practice, this study examined the association among cognitive engagement, metacognitive strategy use, and AI technology utilization in relation to students' reading comprehension skills. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, the study involved 162 Grade 12 students from various strands in selected public secondary schools in Misamis Occidental, chosen through simple random sampling. The information gathered for this study was examined using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to test the study and answer the research questions at the 0.05 significance level. To examine the relationship between the identified independent variables and the dependent variable, a canonical correlation analysis was used. Findings revealed that students demonstrated a high level of metacognitive strategy use, particularly in planning, followed by evaluation and monitoring, and a high level of cognitive engagement in their English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) classes. However, AI tool use was moderate, limited mostly to surface-level tasks such as translation, vocabulary clarification, and grammar checking. In reading comprehension, students performed proficiently in literal and inferential comprehension but only at a basic level in evaluative comprehension. Results further indicated that metacognitive strategies significantly influenced reading comprehension, with planning emerging as the strongest predictor of inferential comprehension. The findings underscore the essential roles of metacognitive regulation and cognitive engagement in AI-

mediated learning environments and recommend integrating metacognitive strategy instruction with engagement-based pedagogies, such as reciprocal teaching and cooperative reading, to strengthen students' comprehension and optimize AI-assisted learning.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools, Metacognitive Strategies, Cognitive Engagement; Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension remains a major challenge in Philippine education. Despite ongoing literacy reforms, many Filipino learners continue to struggle. The 2023 OECD report on the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed that 81% of Filipino students fell below the basic proficiency level in reading, placing the country among the lowest globally (OECD, 2023). Weak reading skills affect not only language learning but also performance in content areas such as science and mathematics, where comprehension is crucial for problem-solving. One factor linked to poor comprehension is limited cognitive engagement, the mental effort and persistence learners invest in understanding texts (Barkley & Major, 2020; Li & Xue, 2023; Wang & Hue, 2025). However, limited empirical evidence examines how this engagement correlates with comprehension in technology-enhanced learning contexts.

The growing use of artificial intelligence (AI) in classrooms has further reshaped reading practices. Studies show that AI tools can enhance comprehension through feedback and scaffolding (Luckin et al., 2016; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019), yet over-reliance on them may hinder independent reasoning and reflection (Ju, 2023; Abdulganie et al., 2025).

Similarly, metacognitive strategies—planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's understanding—are critical for reading success (Ghosh, 2024; Lakha, 2025), but few studies explore how these interact with AI use and engagement. Addressing these gaps, this study examines how metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, and the use of AI tools are associated with reading comprehension among Filipino senior high school students. It contributes to the pursuit of inclusive and quality education (SDG 4) and promotes responsible innovation in learning through educational technology (SDG 9).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is grounded on the assumption that students' use of metacognitive strategies, level of cognitive engagement, and utilization of AI tools is significantly linked to their reading comprehension performance. Reading comprehension is understood as a multidimensional process that includes literal comprehension, the

ability to recall explicit details; inferential comprehension, the skill to deduce meaning and establish relationships beyond what is directly stated; and evaluative comprehension, the capacity to make judgments, assess quality, and form opinions about texts. Achieving proficiency across these levels requires both strategic regulation and meaningful engagement in the reading process.

The study draws on Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988), Automation Bias Theory (Parasuraman & Manzey, 2010), and Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985). These frameworks collectively explain how students think, engage, and regulate their use of technology as they process textual information. Cognitive Load Theory explains that when learners rely too heavily on AI tools for comprehension, they may experience increased extraneous cognitive load, leaving limited mental capacity for deep processing and metacognitive control. Conversely, when AI is used strategically, to clarify complex information, summarize content, or check understanding, it can reduce unnecessary load and support metacognitive planning, monitoring, and evaluation, which are crucial for higher comprehension.

Automation Bias Theory provides insight into students' interactions with AI tools by suggesting that learners may uncritically accept AI-generated outputs, thereby limiting their cognitive and inferential reasoning. This theory emphasizes the importance of metacognitive regulation to counteract such bias, encouraging learners to evaluate, verify, and reflect upon AI-assisted information rather than passively accepting it. Self-Determination Theory, meanwhile, provides the conceptual foundation for cognitive engagement. It posits that when students experience autonomy and competence in their reading tasks, they engage more deeply, persist longer, and process information more meaningfully. Such engagement, paired with deliberate metacognitive strategy use, promotes active construction of meaning rather than mechanical reading.

The interplay among the three independent variables is dynamic. Metacognitive strategies enable students to plan their approach to reading, monitor comprehension as they engage with the text, and evaluate their understanding afterward. Cognitive engagement sustains attention and motivation, prompting deeper interaction with both the text and the learning task. AI tool use, when properly regulated, can scaffold comprehension by offering supplementary explanations or corrective feedback, but when misused, it may encourage cognitive laziness and limit critical thought. In this study, reading comprehension, comprising literal, inferential, and evaluative understanding, serves as the dependent variable, influenced by the degree to which students apply metacognitive strategies, maintain cognitive engagement, and utilize AI tools effectively. It is assumed that students who demonstrate stronger metacognitive control, higher engagement, and strategic use of AI will attain better performance across all comprehension levels. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework illustrating how these three independent variables correlate with reading comprehension skills.

Figure1. Schematic Presentation Showing the Relationship of the Variables in the Study

Research Questions

This paper sought to investigate the association of cognitive engagement, use of metacognitive strategies, and the usage of AI technologies on students' comprehension skills.

Specifically, it aimed to address the following questions:

1. To what extent do the participants use metacognitive strategies in terms of
 - 1.1 Planning;
 - 1.2 Monitoring; and
 - 1.3 Evaluating?
2. What is the participant's assessment of their cognitive engagement during their English Class?
3. To what extent do the participants use Artificial Intelligence tools?
4. What is the participants' level of reading comprehension skills in terms of
 - 4.1 Literal comprehension;
 - 4.2 Inferential comprehension; and
 - 4.3 Evaluative comprehension?
5. Do the participants' extent of use of metacognitive cognitive strategies, cognitive engagement and use of Artificial Intelligence have significant relationship on their reading comprehension skills?

Hypotheses

Research questions 1, 2, 3, and 4 are hypotheses-free while the research question 5 can be hypothesized at a .05 level of significance.

Ho1: The participants' extent of use of metacognitive cognitive strategies does not have significant relationship on their reading comprehension skills.

H₀2: The participants' assessment of cognitive engagement does not have significant relationship on their reading comprehension skills.

H₀3: The participants' extent of use of AI tools does not have significant relationship on their reading comprehension skills.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationships among metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, and AI tool use and students' reading comprehension skills. This design was appropriate for the study because it allowed the researcher to objectively describe the population's characteristics, determine the levels of each variable, and assess the degree of association among them without manipulating any conditions. As Fraenkel and Wallen (2019) emphasize, a correlational approach is appropriate when the goal is to determine whether and to what extent variables are related in a naturally occurring setting. In this context, the design enabled the researcher to identify whether students who are more metacognitively aware, cognitively engaged, and strategic in their use of AI tools perform better in reading comprehension.

Participants

The participants were 162 Grade 12 students enrolled in English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) from selected public secondary schools in Misamis Occidental during the first semester of School Year 2025–2026. The total population consisted of 208 students across the General Academic Strand (GAS), Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) tracks. Using the Taro Yamane formula (1967) with a 5% margin of error, the required sample size was 137; however, to ensure broader representation, data were collected from 162 respondents. Simple random sampling was used to give all students an equal chance of participation. Participants were officially enrolled in EAPP and had prior exposure to AI tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, or translation applications.

Scope and Limitations

This study examined the association among the use of AI tools, metacognitive strategies, and cognitive engagement with students' comprehension skills. The research was conducted during the 2025-2026 school year, specifically in the first semester, at the selected secondary public schools in Misamis Occidental. The participants were Grade 12 students enrolled in English for Academic and Professional Purposes. A total of 208 students came from different strands (General

Academic Strand, Accountancy, Business and Management, and Technology Vocational Livelihood. Using the Taro Yamane formula, the researcher determined that the population sample was 137. However, due to the class size, the researcher collected data from 162 participants. The study further investigated the association of the use of AI tools, metacognitive strategies, and cognitive engagement on students' reading comprehension. A quantitative correlational research design was used to analyze the relationships among these variables, using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Correlational Design: Since a descriptive-correlational design was employed, the study can only establish the degree of association between the variables. It cannot imply cause-and-effect relationships (causality) among AI tool use, metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, and reading comprehension.

Self-Reported Data: Data on metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, and AI tool use were collected via self-report instruments (surveys and questionnaires). Responses may be influenced by participant biases, such as social desirability, leading to potential inaccuracies in the reported levels of engagement and strategy use.

Context Specificity: The results are specific to the Grade 12 EAPP students in the selected public schools in Misamis Occidental during the specified semester. Generalizing these findings to other grade levels, learning areas, private schools, or different geographic regions should be done with caution.

Cross-Sectional Nature: The data were collected at a single point in time, offering a snapshot of the associations. It does not capture changes or developments in the variables over an extended period.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection procedure followed a structured sequence. First, the participants were oriented and guided by the researcher. Next, the four instruments (1) Metacognitive Strategies Questionnaire, (2) the AI Tool Usage Questionnaire, (3) the Cognitive Engagement Scale, and (4) the Reading Comprehension Test, were administered in a single session lasting approximately 60 to 90 minutes. These instruments were printed and distributed to students in their classrooms, which were conducive to learning and data collection. The researcher supervised the process to ensure proper administration and lessen interruptions. After completion, the tests and questionnaires were retrieved and checked for completeness. All responses were encoded and organized for statistical analysis.

Instruments

Four research instruments were used in this study, each aligned with the variables under investigation. The Metacognitive Strategies Scale, adapted from Schraw and

Dennison (1994) Metacognitive Awareness Inventory, measured planning, monitoring, and evaluating processes through a five-point Likert scale to determine how learners regulate their thinking. The Cognitive Engagement Scale, adapted from Wang et al. (2014), assessed students' critical thinking, effort, and persistence in English learning tasks. A researcher-developed AI Tool Usage Questionnaire, based on the frameworks of Holmes et al. (2022) and Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), measured the frequency, purpose, and regulation of AI tool use in reading activities. Finally, the Reading Comprehension Test, which was validated by English teachers and anchored on the frameworks of Snow and the RAND Reading Study Group (2002), evaluated students' literal, inferential, and evaluative comprehension. All instruments were reviewed and validated by experts to ensure reliability, content alignment, and appropriateness for the study's objectives.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instruments

All instruments were validated by three experts in English language teaching, educational research, and educational technology to ensure relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study objectives. The tools were pilot-tested with a similar group of students not included in the main sample to establish reliability. The AI Tool Usage Questionnaire achieved a McDonald's Omega of 0.912, indicating excellent reliability. The Cognitive Engagement Scale obtained an Omega of 0.776, reflecting acceptable reliability. For Metacognitive Strategies, the subscales yielded the following Omega coefficients: Planning = 0.72 (acceptable), Monitoring = 0.71 (acceptable), and Evaluation = 0.615 (low reliability). As a result, items 10, 11, and 12 were rephrased, while items 13 and 14 were removed, leaving three items in the evaluation subscale. The Reading Comprehension Test also demonstrated sound reliability, with Omega coefficients of 0.789 for literal comprehension, 0.743 for inferential comprehension, and 0.785 for evaluative comprehension. The use of McDonald's Omega instead of Cronbach's Alpha is supported by methodological literature indicating that Omega provides a more accurate estimate of reliability when the assumptions underlying Alpha are violated (Orcan, 2023).

Statistical Treatment of the Study

The data gathered were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive statistics, including mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation, were used to summarize participants' metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, AI tool use, and reading comprehension performance. To determine the relationship among these variables, canonical correlation analysis (CCA) was employed to assess the combined association of the independent variables: metacognitive strategies, cognitive engagement, and AI tool use, on reading comprehension. Prior to the analysis, statistical assumptions such as normality, linearity, and multicollinearity were examined through the Shapiro-Wilk test, histograms, Q-Q plots, and variance inflation factors to ensure the validity of results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that participants demonstrated a high overall use of metacognitive strategies ($M = 3.88$, $SD = 0.46$), indicating that they frequently plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning in English classes. Among the three dimensions, planning obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.56$), suggesting that students often set goals and organize tasks before reading or writing activities. Evaluation followed ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.53$), showing that learners regularly reflect on their performance and adjust strategies after completing tasks, while monitoring ranked slightly lower ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 0.63$), which implies that checking comprehension during learning occurs less consistently. These results denote that participants are generally strategic and self-regulated learners who consciously manage their learning processes. This finding supports previous studies (Teng, 2020; Ratnayake et al., 2023; Liu & Li, 2024) that show that high metacognitive awareness enhances engagement, persistence, and overall academic achievement.

Table 1 Summary Table of Participants' Use of Metacognitive Strategies

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Planning	4.02	High	0.56
Monitoring	3.71	High	0.63
Evaluation	3.91	High	0.53
Metacognitive strategies	3.88	High	0.46

Metacognitive Strategies Scoring Procedure to Three Dimensions

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.51-4.50	Agree	High
2.51-3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2 shows that participants exhibited a high level of cognitive engagement in their English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) classes ($M = 3.93$, $SD = 0.51$), indicating that they actively process information, connect lessons to real-life situations, and persist in completing academic tasks. Most participants (62.35%) were classified as highly engaged, while only 1.23% were classified as lowly engaged, reflecting strong intellectual involvement overall. The highest-rated indicator, "I reflect on how English skills learned in EAPP can be useful in future careers" ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 0.74$), reveals that students perceive English learning as meaningful and relevant to their professional growth. This supports Daumiller et al. (2023), who emphasized that learners' recognition of the practical value of learning goals enhances motivation and deepens cognitive engagement.

Table 2 Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of their Cognitive Engagement during their English Class

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	25	15.43
3.51-4.50	High	101	62.35
2.51-3.50	Moderate	34	20.99
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.23
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
	Total	162	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.93	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.51	

For cognitive engagement Scoring Procedure

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.51-4.50	Agree	High
2.51-3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3 shows that participants reported a moderate level of AI tool use in reading and comprehension activities ($M = 3.20$, $SD = 0.55$), indicating they use AI occasionally but not as a primary learning strategy. Over half of the students (53.70%) were moderate users, while 35.19% showed high use, suggesting that AI integration in English learning remains limited or situational. The highest-rated indicator, "I use AI tools to translate unfamiliar or complex vocabulary in a passage" ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.95$), reveals that students primarily rely on AI for translation and word clarification, consistent with Sahari et al. (2025), who found that learners often use AI for surface-level assistance rather than deep comprehension. Other uses, such as explaining difficult passages or identifying main ideas, were rated moderate, reflecting limited engagement in higher-order thinking tasks. The lowest means were observed for routine or test-related AI use, indicating that AI-assisted learning is not yet an established study habit. This pattern aligns with Khosravi et al. (2023), who emphasized that effective AI integration depends on digital literacy and instructional guidance. Overall, the findings suggest that students treat AI as a supplementary reading aid rather than a tool for critical analysis, underscoring the need for reflective, guided AI use to develop comprehension skills.

Table 3 Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the participants' Extent of Use of AI Tools

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	0	0.00
3.51-4.50	High	57	35.19
2.51-3.50	Moderate	87	53.70
1.51-2.50	Low	17	10.49
1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	0.62
Total		162	100.0
		Overall Mean Interpretation	3.20 Moderate
		SD	0.55

Use of AI Scoring Procedure

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51-5.00	Always	Very High
3.51-4.50	Most of the time	High
2.51-3.50	Sometimes	Moderate
1.51-2.50	Rarely	Low
1.00-1.50	Never	Very Low

Overall, students demonstrated proficient comprehension performance, with higher means in literal (M = 3.78) and inferential (M = 3.68) levels, but a notably lower mean in evaluative comprehension (M = 2.09) as shown in Table 4. This indicates that while students can understand explicit and implied meanings, they encounter challenges when required to critically evaluate and judge text content. The results parallel the work of others who identified evaluative comprehension as the most demanding level of reading (Paige et al., 2024). This finding underscores the need to integrate higher-order thinking strategies and critical literacy practices in English instruction.

Table 4 Summary Table of Participants' Reading Comprehension Skills

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Literal	3.78	Proficient	1.15
Inferential	3.68	Proficient	0.86
Evaluative	2.09	Basic	0.91
Reading comprehension	10.48	Proficient	2.28

Literal, Inferential, and Evaluative Comprehension Skills Scoring Procedure

Score Range	Interpretation	Description
4.51-5.00	Excellent Comprehension	Demonstrates advanced comprehension skills; can infer meaning, identify main ideas, and critically

Score Range	Interpretation	Description
3.51-4.50	Proficient Comprehension	evaluate texts with accuracy and insight. Shows deep understanding and strong analytical ability. Exhibits solid comprehension; grasps main ideas and supporting details, and can make reasonable inferences. Occasional lapses in deeper analysis but overall good understanding.
2.51-3.50	Basic Comprehension	Shows partial understanding; identifies general ideas but struggles with implicit meanings, inferences, or evaluation. Needs moderate guidance to improve comprehension.
1.51-2.50	Developing Comprehension	Displays limited understanding; often misinterprets key points or fails to connect ideas. Requires significant support and strategy reinforcement.
1.00-1.50	Needs Improvement	Demonstrates difficulty with basic comprehension; unable to identify main ideas or infer meaning. Requires extensive instruction and remedial practice.

Reading Comprehension Score Range

Score Range	Interpretation
10.41 – 13.00	Excellent – Demonstrates outstanding mastery of the material; comprehension and performance are consistently exceptional.
7.81 – 10.40	Proficient – Shows strong understanding and performance; minor gaps in comprehension.
5.21 – 7.80	Basic – Demonstrates adequate understanding; may have difficulty with complex or detailed items.
2.61 – 5.20	Developing– Shows partial understanding; frequent errors and misinterpretations.
1.00 – 2.60	Needs improvement – Demonstrates minimal comprehension; requires significant intervention and support.

Table 5 presents the results of the canonical correlation analysis, which revealed a statistically significant relationship between participants' metacognitive strategies and their reading comprehension skills ($R = 0.26$, $R^2 = 0.68$, $F = 2.135$, $p = 0.026$). This indicates that approximately 68% of the variance in reading comprehension can be explained by variations in the use of metacognitive strategies. The correlation suggests a low-to-moderate positive relationship, confirming that greater application of metacognitive strategies is associated with better comprehension performance. This supports Flavell (2020) assertion that planning, monitoring, and evaluation enable learners to regulate their cognitive processes, thereby improving understanding and learning outcomes.

Among the metacognitive strategy dimensions, planning (0.58) showed the highest canonical loading, indicating its strong association with reading comprehension. Students who preview texts, set goals, and organize their reading approach tend to

achieve higher comprehension scores, particularly in inferential understanding (0.63), which reflects the ability to interpret meanings beyond surface details. Monitoring (0.11) and evaluating (0.25) showed weaker but supportive roles, suggesting that these processes reinforce comprehension indirectly. These results align with Zhang and Cao (2023), who found that planning behaviors are closely linked to engagement and comprehension in digital reading, and with Paris and Winograd (2022), who emphasized that planning-focused metacognition fosters deeper, inferential comprehension and critical thinking. Overall, the findings affirm that strengthening learners' metacognitive planning can significantly enhance higher-order comprehension skills.

Table 5 Canonical Correlation Analysis of Participants' Assessment of their Metacognitive Strategies and their Reading Comprehension Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R	R ²	F	p
Metacognitive strategies					
Planning	0.58				
Monitoring	0.11				
Evaluating	0.25				
Reading comprehension skills		0.26	0.68	2.135*	0.026
Literal	-0.16				
Inferential	0.63				
Evaluative	0.15				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 6 shows the results of the canonical correlation analysis revealed a statistically non-significant relationship between participants' assessment of their cognitive engagement and their reading comprehension skills, with a canonical correlation coefficient ($R = 0.20$) and a corresponding $R^2 = 0.41$. This means that only 41% of the shared variance between the two sets of variables is explained by the model, leaving 59% variance unaccounted for, indicating a weak and unstable association. The F-value of 2.271 and p-value of 0.082 ($p > 0.05$) indicates the relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_02) is not rejected, implying the students' level of cognitive engagement do not reliably predict their comprehension performance. Students may appear cognitively engaged, showing effort or attention, but this engagement might not translate into deep processing of text. It is likely to happen that their engagement may focus on task completion rather than meaningful comprehension.

This finding furthermore aligns with the claims of Fredricks et al. (2021), who explains that cognitive engagement, while theoretically linked to comprehension through attention and investment in learning tasks, may not directly translate to measurable

improvements in reading comprehension unless combined with effective strategies such as planning and monitoring. Similarly, Wang and Eccles (2022) emphasized that cognitive engagement alone may be insufficient for enhancing higher-order comprehension skills without guided metacognitive support.

Table 6 Canonical Correlation Analysis of Participants' Assessment of Cognitive Engagement and their Reading Comprehension Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R	R ²	F	p
Cognitive engagement	0.20				
Reading comprehension skills					
Literal	0.17	0.20	0.41	2.271	0.082
Inferential	-0.15				
Evaluative	-0.05				

Table 7 reveals a non-significant relationship between AI tool use and reading comprehension ($R = 0.17$, $R^2 = 0.029$, $F(2,135) = 1.545$, $p = 0.205$), indicating that the frequency of AI use did not meaningfully associate with students' reading comprehension. The result supports the findings of Luckin et al. (2020) and Holmes et al. (2021), who emphasized that AI tools enhance learning only when paired with deliberate cognitive strategies and reflective use. Without guided instruction and metacognitive regulation, reliance on AI tends to remain surface-level, limiting its potential to improve comprehension outcomes.

Table 7 Canonical Correlation Analysis of Participants' Assessment of their Use of AI tools and their Reading Comprehension Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R	R ²	F	p
Use of AI tools	0.17				
Reading comprehension skills					
Literal	-0.15	0.17	0.029	1.545	0.205
Inferential	-0.01				
Evaluative	0.02				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Conclusions

Overall, the study concludes that effective metacognitive regulation, particularly strategic planning, is central role in enhancing reading comprehension, while cognitive engagement and AI tool use require structured guidance and purposeful integration to be effective. Consistent with Cognitive Load Theory, students who consciously plan, monitor,

and evaluate their learning demonstrate better comprehension, as these processes help manage cognitive demands and promote meaningful understanding. Although students showed high cognitive engagement in English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) classes, the results, in line with Self-Determination Theory, suggest that motivation and persistence alone are insufficient without metacognitive control to translate engagement into comprehension gains. The moderate and largely surface-level use of AI tools reflects Automation Bias Theory, indicating that unreflective dependence on technology provides limited cognitive benefits. Grounded in Constructivist Learning Theory, the findings further underscore that evaluative comprehension remains a developing skill that requires explicit instruction in reasoning, analysis, and critical reading. Collectively, the results affirm that metacognitive regulation is foundational to reading comprehension, and that engagement and AI use must be scaffolded within reflective, strategy-oriented instruction to foster higher-order literacy skills.

Recommendations

The findings present meaningful implications for classroom instruction, curriculum design, and research. In teaching practice, integrating explicit modeling of metacognitive strategies through reflective journals, self-assessment, and think-aloud activities may help students internalize planning, monitoring, and evaluation processes. Ethical and purposeful use of AI tools can be encouraged through guided workshops and classroom integration that emphasize critical reasoning rather than surface-level correction. Curriculum development may benefit from incorporating metacognitive training with engagement-based approaches such as reciprocal teaching, guided inquiry, and cooperative reading to strengthen comprehension. At the institutional level, policies promoting human-centered and reflective AI use can support sustainable digital learning practices. Professional development initiatives that enhance teachers' competence in fostering metacognitive regulation, engagement, and AI literacy are likewise valuable. Future studies may consider broader samples or experimental designs to further examine how structured metacognitive instruction and AI integration influence comprehension and related cognitive factors such as motivation and digital literacy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study rigorously adhered to ethical research principles, ensuring participant rights and well-being through several key procedures. Since participants were minors, the researchers secured parental/guardian consent and also obtained student assent to respect their autonomy, a practice aligned with the Belmont Report. To guarantee confidentiality and anonymity, no names were recorded, and responses were assigned unique codes, with all data stored securely and used solely for the study. Furthermore, participation was completely voluntary, and the fair selection of participants ensured no group was burdened, while a safety monitoring plan confirmed the research posed no physical or medical risks.

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